

Deliverable A4.1 “Report on landscape, environmental, ecological and socio-economic indicators in case study areas”

Project ref. number	LIFE20 PRE/IT/000007
Project title	Remote sensing oriented nature-based solutions towards a NEW LIFE FOR DRYLANDS
Project Acronym	NewLife4Drylands

Deliverable title	Report on landscape, environmental, ecological and socio-economic indicators in case study areas
Deliverable number	A4.1
Deliverable version	V.2: Final version
Contractual date of delivery	30/06/2023
Actual date of delivery	31/01/2024
Online access	Yes
Diffusion	Public
Nature of deliverable	Technical
Action	A4
Partner responsible	SAPIENZA
Author(s)	Marcello Vitale, Vito Emanuele Cambria, Martina Perez
Editor	Marcello Vitale

Executive summary

The present document stands for the first Deliverable of Action A4 delivered on January 2024. It provides a detailed analysis of the environmental challenges encountered at each project site. It offers a comprehensive examination of the several factors contributing to these problems, including natural phenomena and human activities. The report also reviews past studies and projects that have tried to identify potential solutions to minimize the impacts on semi-arid and arid ecosystems. By presenting a thorough overview of the issues at hand, the report aims to facilitate a more informed and effective approach to environmental management and conservation. Significant emphasis was placed on analysing the potential socio-economic outcomes of worsening environmental conditions at the sites under investigation. In paragraph 7, the effectiveness of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) applications for addressing environmental challenges at each of the study sites has been discussed. The success of these NbSs was heavily dependent on the specific social and economic characteristics of each site. To achieve desirable outcomes, NbS interventions needed to be tailored to the unique needs and priorities of the surrounding communities. It also highlighted the importance of considering the long-term economic and social sustainability of NbS interventions when planning and implementing them. The comprehensive report provides a detailed account of the methods used and proposed solutions for the given problem, which are supported by a thoroughly researched reference bibliography.

Table of Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Landscape, environmental, ecological, and socio-economic indicators for the Palo Laziale wood (Central Italy).....	8
3. Landscape, environmental, ecological, and socio-economic indicators for the Nestos Delta Area (East Macedonia, Greece).....	15
4. Landscape, environmental, ecological, and socio-economic indicators for the Alta Murgia National Park (Southern Italy).....	24
5. Landscape, environmental, ecological, and socio-economic indicators for the El Bruc site (North/Western Spain) and the Tifaracàs site (Canary Islands, Spain).....	33
6. Landscape, environmental, ecological, and socio-economic indicators for the Asterousia Mountains (Crete, Southern Greece)	47
7. The Social Dimension of Nature-Based Solutions (NbSs)	544

Introduction

Desertification is a phenomenon that occurs when once-fertile land becomes a desert due to climatic changes or human activities. The climate crisis is exacerbating desertification, which is now one of the most pressing ecological concerns. Dry, arid, semi-arid, and sub-humid areas, known as "drylands," are particularly vulnerable to desertification. Unfortunately, these regions make up 41% of the Earth's land surface and are home to around two billion people (Rodrigues do Nascimento, 2023). Desertification has a profound impact on human well-being and can impede efforts to address the effects of climate change (Briassoulis, 2019). It disrupts nutrient cycles and reduces primary production and microbial activity, leading to soil degradation and loss of biodiversity. This, in turn, hinders efforts to capture carbon and control dust storms and floods. The consequences of desertification can also contribute to its cause, creating a harmful cycle. Therefore, combating desertification has become a major global environmental challenge that requires a comprehensive approach. However, at the local level, desertification can be exacerbated by multiple factors, including population pressure, political and socioeconomic scenarios, land use and management, and climate-related processes (Pal et al., 2023). Droughts, poor soils, steep slopes, forest fires, unsustainable agriculture and livestock practices, and overpopulation are some of the main aggravating factors at the local level. These factors can directly affect vegetation and its growth, and many of them are present in the Mediterranean region. Restoring degraded land is essential for preserving the integrity of forests, rangelands, mine-affected areas, and many habitats that support valuable biodiversity. Ecological restoration represents a holistic process aimed at fully repairing ecosystem structure, function, and the provision of goods and services (SER, 2004). It provides a conceptual framework where the link between nature and culture is especially inspiring. Ecological restoration is a process of assisting the recovery of an ecosystem that has been degraded, damaged, or destroyed (SCBD (2010). An ecosystem has recovered when it contains sufficient biotic and abiotic resources to continue its development without further assistance or subsidy, and it sustains itself structurally and functionally. A restored ecosystem demonstrates resilience to normal ranges of environmental stress and disturbance and interacts with contiguous ecosystems in terms of biotic and abiotic flows and cultural interactions. The restoration process aims to return an

ecosystem to its historic trajectory. The historic trajectory of a severely impacted ecosystem may be difficult or impossible to determine with accuracy. Nevertheless, the general direction and boundaries of that trajectory may be set up by combining knowledge of past ecosystem structure, composition, and functioning, comparisons with less degraded ecosystems, and reference information on the ecological, cultural, and historical context (SER, 2004). Restoration projects must be planned to restore the structure and function of ecosystems. However, deciding which interventions are needed to achieve this goal is one of the biggest challenges. Frequently, human activities have directly or indirectly caused or exacerbated the degradation, damage, transformation, or destruction of the ecosystem that requires restoration, such as pollution, overgrazing, soil erosion or compaction, drainage, structural damage, high-grade logging, and alien species invasion. In some cases, natural factors such as wildfires, floods, storms, or volcanic eruptions have also contributed to the impacts on ecosystems. Although ecological restoration is not always possible to achieve, it is one of the most effective ways to restore degraded ecosystems and improve their health, integrity, and sustainability (van Andel & Aronson, 2012). The restoration process may be challenging, but it is essential for preserving the natural resources that support human well-being. The level of degradation in an ecosystem directly impacts the complexity of interventions required to restore it (Ghazoul & Chazdon, 2017). In slightly degraded ecosystems, management practices aimed at removing stressors may be sufficient to restore the system's functionality and prevent further degradation. However, in more severe cases, in addition to removing existing degradation factors, it may be necessary to make biological modifications or to restore physical and/or chemical environmental conditions, or both. In the most extreme cases, the entire ecosystem may be devastated, requiring the restoration of vegetation cover, soil, and the original morphology. To determine the type of intervention required, several factors must be considered, including the biocenosis status, such as the state of the soil seed bank, seedling proportion surviving after the last disturbance, number of breeding individuals, presence of wildlife, and more (Calistri et al., 2013). Moreover, abiotic parameters, such as rainfall and temperature regime, soil status and characteristics, erosion levels, and more, must also be considered. The current threats, potential risk factors, and surrounding environmental conditions can also influence the intervention. Numerous technical difficulties can arise during the restoration process, including

adverse topographical conditions, accessibility, nature of the substrate, lack of availability of suitable plants and seeds, and the absence of knowledge about the seedlings' establishment ability of species to be introduced and nursery cultivation techniques that favour it (Chirino et al., 2009; Ramón Vallejo et al., 2012; Valliere et al., 2022). Furthermore, the socio-economic context in which the project will operate plays a significant role in the planning, implementation, and monitoring of the project, affecting its success (Nilsson et al., 2016; Li et al., 2017). Therefore, it is critical to consider the community's expectations around the project and the financial means available before embarking on restoration efforts.

Under these premises, the NewLife4Drylands project considers six pilot sites found in Spain (Tifaracàs, El Bruc), Italy (Palo Laziale, Alta Murgia), and Greece (Nestos, Mt. Asterousia). They are a set of case studies with distinctive characteristics to design and deliver the general model for desertification monitoring of degraded areas based on remote sensing indicators and the protocol for NBS application for dryland restoration. This deliverable is dedicated to linking the case studies with the previous actions from restoration projects.

Essential Bibliography

Briassoulis, H. (2019). Combating land degradation and desertification: The land-use planning quandary. *Land*, 8(2), 27.

Calistri, P., Iannetti, S., L. Danzetta, M., Narcisi, V., Cito, F., Di Sabatino, D., Bruno, R., Sauro, F., Atzeni, M., Carvelli, A. and Giovannini, A. (2013), The Components of 'One World – One Health' Approach. *Transbound Emerg Dis*, 60: 4-13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/tbed.12145>

Chirino, E., Vilagrosa, A., Cortina, J., Valdecantos, A., Fuentes, D., Trubat, R., ... & Vallejo, V. R. (2009). Ecological restoration in degraded drylands: the need to improve the seedling quality and site conditions in the field. *Forest management*, 85-158.

Ghazoul, J., & Chazdon, R. (2017). Degradation and recovery in changing forest landscapes: a multiscale conceptual framework. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 42, 161-188.

Li, T., Lü, Y., Fu, B., Comber, A. J., Harris, P., & Wu, L. (2017). Gauging policy-driven large-scale vegetation restoration programmes under a changing environment: Their effectiveness and socio-economic relationships. *Science of the Total Environment*, 607, 911-919.

Nilsson, C., Aradottir, A. L., Hagen, D., Halldórsson, G., Høegh, K., Mitchell, R. J., ... & Wilson, S. D. (2016). Evaluating the process of ecological restoration. *Ecology and Society*, 21(1).

Pal, S. C., Chatterjee, U., Chakraborty, R., Roy, P., Chowdhuri, I., Saha, A., ... & Islam, M. K. (2023). Anthropogenic drivers induced desertification under changing climate: Issues, policy interventions, and the way forward. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 20, 100303.

Ramón Vallejo, V., Smanis, A., Chirino, E., Fuentes, D., Valdecantos, A., & Vilagrosa, A. (2012). Perspectives in dryland restoration: approaches for climate change adaptation. *New Forests*, 43(5-6), 561-579.

Rodrigues do Nascimento (2023). Causes and Impacts of Desertification in the World. In: Global Environmental Changes, Desertification and Sustainability. SpringerBriefs in Latin American Studies. Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-32947-0_4

SCBD (2010). Strategic Plan for Biodiversity 2011–2020 and the Aichi Target: Living in Harmony with Nature. CBD Secretariat, Montreal. URL: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/decisions/cop-10/cop-10-dec-02-en.pdf>

Valliere, J. M., Ruscalleda Alvarez, J., Cross, A. T., Lewandrowski, W., Riviera, F., Stevens, J. C., ... & Veneklaas, E. J. (2022). Restoration ecophysiology: an ecophysiological approach to improve restoration strategies and outcomes in severely disturbed landscapes. *Restoration Ecology*, 30, e13571.

van Andel J & Aronson J (eds.). 2012. *Restoration Ecology: The New Frontier*. 2nd Edition, Blackwell Publishing Ltd, Oxford, UK.

Landscape, environmental, ecological, and socio-economic indicators for the Palo Laziale wood (Central Italy)

Ladispoli is a coastal town of about 41,000 inhabitants (Fig. 1). From a touristic point of view, it is strategically located, as it is approximately 30 km away from both Civitavecchia and Rome, to which it is well connected by rail. Ladispoli was part of Southern Etruria and is therefore an area rich in history. Here, necropolis, Roman villas, castles, ancient roads, and houses, as well as historical heritages can be found. The city of Ladislao was founded in 1888 at the behest of Prince Ladislaus Odescalchi who assigned part of his estate of Palo, between the ditches and Vaccina Sanguinara, to create the actual natural area of Palo Laziale wood under the administration of the Odescalchi family.

Fig. 1 – The municipality of Ladispoli is in the background and a great part of the Palo Lazio wood is below.

Palo Laziale is a forested area of about 50 ha, located 230 meters from the sea, with an altitude between 3 and 10 meters a.s.l. Apart from being a Site of Community Importance (SCI IT6030022) belonging to the Natura 2000 network, it is also part of the areas involved in the LifePRIMED project (LIFE17 NAT/GR00511-Restoration, management and valorisation of PRiority habitats or MEDiterranean coastal areas) aimed to improve the conservation status of habitats and species of the Palo Laziale Wood through local monitoring and management actions (<https://www.lifeprimed.eu/en/>). Palo Laziale is a mixed Mediterranean forest with high density. *Quercus cerris*, *Quercus pubescens*, *Quercus ilex*, *Fraxinus angustifolia subs. oxycarpa* constitute the highest layer of the forest (about 7-10 meters high). *Laurus nobilis* and *Phillyrea*

latifolia constitute the lower layer of the lowland forest (about 4-5 meters high). The high Mediterranean shrub consists of *Phillyrea latifolia*, *Pistacia lentiscus*, and *Laurus nobilis*. The area was a coppice until 1975 when its management passed to the WWF. Due to the lack of silvicultural management, the gradual aging of the forest has led to a weakening of resistance against both drought and pathogenic fungi. Coppice abandonment might lead to dominance, at the landscape level, of senescent woodlands and the loss of the earlier successional stages of forest ecosystems (Mairota et al., 2016). Between 2000 and 2003, approximately four thousand *Quercus* individuals (covering about 20 hectares) succumbed to the combined effects of severe summer drought stress and the rapid spread of the *Biscogniauxia mediterranea* fungus. Research findings underscore the significance of *B. mediterranea*'s high genetic variability (Henriques et al., 2014) and its heterothallic mating system in shaping its adaptive strategy and epidemiology. These factors become even more critical in the context of climate change, which appears to amplify the impact of charcoal disease in *Quercus* forests (Lindner et al., 2010). According to the bioclimatic characteristics of the area, the site is characterised by a Mediterranean climate with rainfall concentrated in winter and autumn and aridity during the summer. The soil is clay-loam consisting of 45% silt, 34% clay, and 21% sand. Currently, the Palo Laziale wood is involved in a series of experimental activities at different spatial and temporal scales which are focused on the ecological restoration of the area. In particular, it supports the recovery of secondary succession which will lead to the forest coverage of the area affected by the die-back phenomenon. As already mentioned, these activities are ongoing within the LIFE PRIMED project. LIFE PRIMED is an important opportunity for making and evaluating restoration and management actions able to break the decline of Mediterranean coastal ecosystems caused by a synergy of different stress factors, particularly those related to climate change and forest management. It aims at improving the conservation status of habitats and species in the Palo Laziale wood site. Reversal of forest decline via improving the chemical-physical conditions of the soil in the 'Pannonian-Balkan turkey oak-sessile oak forests by supplying water during the dry season through a self-sustainable hydraulic system.

To this end, the in-depth analysis of the climatic historical series and the design and construction of a modular and eco-compatible hydraulic structure were two important processes that allowed us to create an ecological restoration project focused on supporting the

ongoing secondary plant succession. A series of structural and functional indicators were considered both derived from remote sensing and from modelling applications focused on the estimation of important processes such as gross and net primary productivity (GPP and NPP, respectively (tC/ha y)), canopy transpiration (E, tH₂O/ha y) and the water use efficiency defined as the ratio between NPP and E (tC/tH₂O).

In parallel, a series of direct and satellite-derived indicators were found, calculated, and spatialized for the area of interest. The following Table 1 shows the main indicators of the functional state of the forest and land degradation and desertification, also in according to the SDG 15.3.1 indicators of the UNCCD, applied to Palo Laziale wood and fully explained in the Deliverable A2.1 “Indicators for the evaluation of restoration actions to combat degradation/desertification”.

Table 1. A series of RS-based indicators were used to investigate the functional state of the Palo Laziale site.

SITE	INDICATOR	SENSOR	SPATIAL RESOLUTION (meters)	SPATIAL FRAME	TEMPORAL FRAME	VALIDATION GROUND DATA	NOTES
PALO LAZIALE	PHENOLOGY TREND (by considering different vegetation indices)	QUICKBIRD	2.4	Natura 2000 Boundary +1 km buffer	2002-2009 (1 image per year)	Available ground data	2004: sick trees cutting
	LAND COVER MAP	PLEIADES	2		2020-2021 (4 multi-season images)		
	HABITAT MAP						
	BURNED AREAS COVER TREND	LANDSAT SENTINEL-2	30_10	2002-2021 (inter-annual time series)			
	LAI ESTIMATIONS	SENTINEL-2 (by Sen2Cor)	10	Only for those LC classes for which on-ground data are available	2015; 2020	Evapotranspiration from the canopy which, by ingestion into modelling, can obtain LAI estimations (2020)	

	FAPAR ESTIMATIONS (for GPP)	SENTINEL-2 PRISMA				Available ground data (2020)	Possible super-resolution or pan-sharpened techniques for PRISMA data
	HISTORICAL CLIMATE ANALYSIS						

It is important to report here that the different approaches adopted in LIFE PRIMED are multi-scale both spatial and temporal. This led to the application of the so-called dual approach, to accurately assess the state of an ecosystem. This involves integrating both *top-down* and *bottom-up* approaches. The top-down approach in restoration ecology is when you start from the goal of restoring the biodiversity and ecosystem functions and services of a degraded area, and then implement actions that target the key drivers of degradation, such as invasive species, pollution, or overexploitation. The structural and functional aspects of Mediterranean and non-Mediterranean ecosystems are dynamic in terms of their spatial and temporal characteristics, which can vary depending on the scale being used. Consequently, determining the health state of an ecosystem requires quantification at multiple scales. Therefore, since most ecological restoration activities are carried out locally, it is necessary to quantify the structural and functional parameters that define the ecosystem's health state at a local scale (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2 Relationship between spatial and temporal resolutions, and processes involved for each time-space resolution.

This dual approach allowed us to integrate different spatial-temporal scales into a unified vision of the ecological restoration process. Under these operational conditions, remote sensing and ground-based indicators have characterised this coastal Mediterranean system. A list of indicators is shown in Table 2 as follows.

Table 2 - Spectral Indices from remote sensing data useful for Land Degradation assessment, the Land Degradation process they can investigate, and Physiological/Environmental parameters measured at the ground level are reported.

Vegetation indices	Degradation processes
NDVI Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	Decline in Biodiversity.
GNDVI Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	Decline in Biomass.
MSAVI2 Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	Decline in vegetation community functioning.
EVI2 Enhanced Vegetation Index2	Decline in vegetation cover.
LAI Leaf Area Index	Decline in primary productivity.
Water indices	
NDWI1 Normalized Difference Water Index 1	Decline in vegetation.
Drought/Dryness indices	
NDDI Normalized Difference Drought Index	Aridification.
SPEI Standardised Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index	
Physiological Parameters	Environmental Parameters
AI/An Leaf/canopy Net photosynthesis	VWC Volumetric water content
EI/Ec Leaf/canopy transpiration	TI/Ta/Ts Leaf/air/soil temperature
WUE Water Use Efficiency (Net Photosynthesis/transpiration ratio)	VPA/VPL Air and saturated vapour pressures
GPP/NPP Gross/Net Primary Productivity	RH Air relative Humidity
	VPD

	Leaf-to-air vapour pressure difference
	PAR Photosynthetic Active Radiation
	FPAR Fraction Photosynthetic Active Radiation

As part of the activities envisaged by the LIFE PRIMED project, floristic and vegetational assessment (phytosociological relieves) characterized the species composition of the plant community living at the Palo Laziale site. These studies have made it possible to evaluate the current structural and functional state of the impacted vegetation and, at the same time, to monitor the progress of vegetative recovery with particular attention to the target habitats to be preserved (Mediterranean temporary ponds, code 3170*, Arborescent matorral with *Laurus nobilis* - code 5230*, and Pannonian-Balkan turkey oak-sessile oak forests - code 91M0).

Finally, the creation of an underground tank (Fig. 3), supplied by appropriately intercepted rainwater, will be the basis for a "one shot" water supply during the period of greatest summer aridity directed to the area most affected by vegetation growth (in secondary succession) after the fungal attack *Biscogniauxia mediterranea* and the consequent deforestation and structural alteration of the vegetation. The system uses hydraulic solutions as a demonstrative character to restore degraded forest ecosystems. It is a practical choice for adapting to climate change and mitigating its effects. The gravity-fed network allows for energy independence and reduced environmental impact, while the underground tank ensures minimal visual impact. The channels are covered with local excavation material, eliminating the need for concrete. The water accumulated in the underground tank is released onto a forest surface of about five hectares by a remotely controlled pumping system powered by solar panels. The network of channels holds micro-cracked pipes (Fig. 3) that guarantee a requisite amount of moisture in the soil during dry months, allowing the maintenance of suffering tree species.

Fig. 3 Underground tanks positioned in the selected area (left), and particular of the micro-perforated pipes (right). Images from the LIFE PRIMED website ([C.3: Hydraulic interventions for habitat recovery and conservation \(lifeprimed.eu\)](http://C.3: Hydraulic interventions for habitat recovery and conservation (lifeprimed.eu))).

Essential Bibliography

Henriques, J., Nóbrega, F., Sousa, E., & Lima, A. (2014). Diversity of *Biscogniauxia mediterranea* within single stromata on cork oak. *Journal of Mycology*, 2014.

Lindner, M., Maroschek, M., Netherer, S., Kremer, A., Barbati, A., Garcia-Gonzalo, J., ... & Marchetti, M. (2010). Climate change impacts, adaptive capacity, and vulnerability of European forest ecosystems. *Forest ecology and management*, 259(4), 698-709.

Mairota, P., Buckley, P., Suchomel, C., Heinsoo, K., Verheyen, K., Hédli, R., ... & Carpanelli, A. (2016). Integrating conservation objectives into forest management: coppice management and forest habitats in Natura 2000 sites. *IForest*, 9(4), 560-568.

Landscape, environmental, ecological and socio-economic indicators for the Nestos Delta Area (East Macedonia, Greece)

The Nestos River, 234 km long, rises in the Rila Mountains (southern Bulgaria) and flows into the Thracian Sea, forming the natural boundary between the Regions of Macedonia and Thrace, in northeastern Greece. Before it reaches the sea, the main river spreads over the coastal plain of Chrysoupolis where it forms a fan-shaped deltaic system with freshwater lakes and ponds, the Nestos delta. The delta, created by the alluvial deposits of the river, covers an area of about 55,000 ha from the bridge near the town of Toxotes (northernmost point) to the coast opposite the island of Thassos (southernmost area). The eastern side of the delta reaches the lagoons of Avdira. On the western side, instead, there are nine other lagoons: Vassova, Erateino, Agiasma, Kokkala, Haidefto, Keramoti, Gefyraki, Palaias Koitis of Nestos and Monastiraki. The lagoons are surrounded by extensive salt marshes and are the home of the most productive fish farms in Greece. The Nestos site is the largest remaining riparian forest in the Mediterranean area, protected within the Delta Nestou Natura 2000 site (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4 A particular of the mouth of the Nestos River where are evident the characteristic coastal lagoons (Habitat target, code 1150*). (Image from Riverland. All rights reserved - 2021 <https://riverland.gr/nestos-delta/>).

This is of great ornithological value, but in past decades has been severely reduced in size. Habitats and species in both Natura 2000 sites face several serious threats, including shrub expansion and invasive species encroachment, eutrophication, and inappropriate forest and water management. These pressures are related both to direct and indirect human actions which expose the forest ecosystems to multiple stress factors. In Nestos, bad water management has contributed to worsening the conservation status of the riparian forest. A significant characteristic of the area is the riparian forest known as "Kotza Orman" (Great Forest), one of the largest of its type in the Mediterranean basin which, although it has been reduced from 12,000 hectares in 1920 to just 2,000 (60 ha have been reforested thanks to another Life Natura project "LIFE NESTOS - LIFE02 NAT/GR/008489"), it remains the largest of all-natural riparian forests in Greece (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5 Riparian Forest along the Nestos River and near grassland areas where target habitats such as temporary ponds (Mediterranean temporary ponds, code 3170*) may be found. (Photo from the LIFE PRIMED project, [Gallery \(lifepimed.eu\)](https://lifelifeprimed.eu/gallery)).

However, at its current status, the forest is affected by several pressures and threats, including lack of water resource management, climate change, expansion of agricultural activities, species disturbance by various human activities, and the degradation of key habitats, such as Mediterranean temporary ponds (habitat 3170*). The Project offers the

opportunity to apply a set of management and restoration actions to halt the decline of this peculiar Mediterranean coastal ecosystem. The "Nestos Delta" is a pilot area where the EU-funded project LIFE PRIMED (LIFE17NAT/GR/000511) will test the effectiveness of concrete conservation measures, including forestry and hydraulic works, to propose an integrated approach to promoting the recovery and long-term conservation of similar ecosystems in other geographical contexts. Also in the case of the Nestos delta site, data on biodiversity and forests were integrated with spatial and satellite data to allow a better assessment of the conservation status of the habitats considered after the interventions of the LIFE PRIMED project (e.g. reforestation programs, assessment of the temporary ponds and floristic species composition, eradication of the infesting plants) and at a broader geographical scale (regional level); hydrogeological data (where available) were integrated with satellite measurements to verify the success of the hydraulic systems in terms of increasing soil water availability over the year. Of particular importance was the analysis of the historical series of climate data for the assessment of the climate trend to evaluate the impact of the identified threats and provide input for modelling and planning further direct conservation actions.

The main threats affecting the Nestos River area can essentially be traced back to four:

- a) *Expansion of shrubs and Alien invasive species.* The uncontrolled growth of shrubs poses a great threat to the habitats of both 3170* and 91E0*. In 3170*, shrubs cover ponds and displace the less competitive typical temporary pond flora. Moreover, the deposition and decomposition of leaves create a deep layer of soil and litter that makes for an inhospitable substrate. In 91E0*, the more aggressive shrubs like *Amorpha fruticosa* take up space that would otherwise be available for *Alnus* and other saplings. Also, the shade created by these shrubs inhibits the growth of *Alnus*, *Salix*, *Populus*, and other saplings, thereby reducing natural regeneration. Three alien invasive species, namely *A. fruticosa*, *P. dioica*, and *A. negundo*, are out-competing indigenous species in 91E0* and are also encroaching on 3170*.
- b) *Illegal logging.* Forest management in the Nestos SCI is targeting preservation of the riparian vegetation and there is no commercial logging in habitat 91E0*. However, the forest structure is significantly affected by illegal logging, which has noticeably increased

in recent years because of the economic crisis and lack of awareness of local people about its importance.)

- c) *Modifications in and/or lack of appropriate water diet.* The flora and fauna of areas 3170 and 91E0 are extremely sensitive to changes in the hydrological cycle as their life cycle is dependent on regular alternation of wet and dry phases. In the winter of 2016-2017, the ponds held water for only about two months, compared to the average of six months. This resulted in the specialised vegetation not being able to complete its life cycle. Furthermore, the lack of flooding in 91E0 means that no transportation of nutrient-rich sediments can enrich the soils. It is currently unclear whether this is due to changes in the hydrological functions of the river, such as channel movement and silting, or reduced flow caused by retention in the artificial reservoirs upstream, which have inadequate minimal environmental flow.
- d) *Degradation of 3170* through overgrazing, trampling, etc.* Access to temporary ponds is not restricted, which means that grazing animals can damage the vegetation, especially during the short flowering period of the characteristic plants. Cattle presence may also affect water quality and vegetation by excess trampling and the possible increase in nitrates, which can promote the propagation of competing species. Trampling by vehicles (of farmers, hunters, off-road enthusiasts, etc.) at the temporary ponds is a frequent occurrence and can cause structural damage to the plants, as well as compaction of the soil, making it unsuitable for the growth of the characteristic temporary pond species.

The following Table 3 shows the main indicators of the functional state of the forest and land degradation and desertification, also in according to the SDG 15.3.1 indicators of the UNCCD, applied to the Nestos River site and fully explained in the Deliverable A2.1 "Indicators for the evaluation of restoration actions to combat degradation/desertification".

Table 3 - A series of RS-based indicators used to investigate the functional state of the Nestos River site.

SITE	INDICATORS	SENSOR	SPATIAL RESOLUTION (meters)	SPATIAL FRAME	TEMPORAL FRAME	VALIDATION GROUND DATA	NOTES
NESTOS RIVER	LAND COVER MAP	LANDSAT SENTINEL-2	30_10	NATURA 2K +5 km buffer	2000;2005;2010; 2017;2021	Available ground data	
	INVASIVE SPECIES MAP	SENTINEL-2	10		2018; 2021-2022	Drone acquisitions	In 2020 (Autumn) cutting invasive species starts
	HYDROPERIOD INDEX			October 2017-september 2018; October 2019-september 2020;October 2021-september 2022	Available ground data		
	LAI ESTIMATIONS			SENTINEL-2 (by Sen2Cor)	Only for those LC classes for which ground data are available	2015; 2021	Canopy Evapotranspiration ---->LAI (2021)
	HISTORICAL CLIMATE ANALYSIS	Chelsa and ERA5 Land	1km (Chelsa) 9km (ERA5-Land)	NATURA 2K +5 km buffer	Daily stats 1981-2005 Hourly 1979-2021	Local weather stations	

The dual top-down and bottom-up approach, already used for the Palo Laziale wood site, was also used for the Nestos River delta site. Given the scarcity of ground data, the analyses dedicated to the functioning of riparian and non-riparian habitats were carried out through the analysis of satellite data which supplied some inputs for the calculation of the inter-annual variations of the hydrological balance for the entire riverbed. In fact, in addition to the threats already mentioned above, there is another that has been little examined in the past, but which stands for a potential obstacle to ecological restoration programs focused on the area. Since the flow of the Nestos River is controlled by three dams found upstream, there is a series of floods during the hydrological year due to the release of water masses by the dams. These floods occur in winter due to the disposal of excess water due to rainfall in

the Rila mountains (on the border between Greece and Bulgaria), but also in summer due to the need for greater energy production for the sustenance of the higher consumption due to the use of air conditioners. Non-seasonal floods cause serious functional stress to the riparian vegetation but also to the surrounding herbaceous and shrubby vegetation, in some cases favouring the territorial spread of *A. fruticosa* to the detriment of native plant species. Furthermore, since the availability of water on the ground may not be adequate for the phenological rhythm of the species characteristic of the temporary ponds, we could see the progressive reduction of these target habitats.

From 2018, these pressures and threats are targeted by a set of restoration interventions that are under implementation in the framework of the LIFE PRIMED. These measures include the development of a hydraulic system to make the ecosystem more resilient to external pressures, the installation of information boards and awareness-raising campaigns to reduce illegal logging and trampling, and field assessment and control by the removal of invasive plant species. Under these operational conditions, remote sensing and ground-based indicators have characterised this riparian ecosystem. A list of indicators is shown in Table 4 as follows.

Table 4 – Several RS-based indices are found here to evaluate the time-space degradation levels and physiological state of the Nestos River site.

Vegetation indices	Degradation processes
NDVI Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	Decline in Biodiversity.
GNDVI Green Normalized Difference Vegetation Index	Decline in Biomass.
MSAVI2 Modified Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index	Decline in vegetation community functioning.
EVI2 Enhanced Vegetation Index2	Decline in vegetation cover.
LAI Leaf Area Index	Decline in primary productivity.
Water indices	
NDWI1 Normalized Difference Water Index 1	Decline in vegetation.
Drought/Dryness indices	

NDDI Normalized Difference Drought Index	Aridification.
SPEI Standardised Precipitation-Evapotranspiration Index	
Physiological Parameters	Environmental Parameters
GPP/NPP Gross/Net Primary Productivity	VWC Volumetric water content
E Transpiration at the stand level	T Surface temperature
WUE Water Use Efficiency (NPP/E ratio)	VPA/VPL Air and saturated vapour pressures
	RH Air relative Humidity
	PAR Photosynthetic Active Radiation
	FPAR Fraction Photosynthetic Active Radiation

An often-underestimated aspect is the analysis of the structure and species composition of the study areas. As part of the activities of the LIFE PRIMED project, field activities were planned which had the aim of quantifying a series of allometric parameters and derived ones, as well as clarifying the species composition of the riparian and non-riparian community and the floristic-vegetation analysis. The purpose of the activities is to quantify the current state of conservation and the ecological trend of the alluvial forest 91E0* in the Nestos Delta. This preparatory study, therefore, can be a key step to assess the condition of the forest ecosystem that will provide important indications about the structure and dynamism of the woodland. This process is essential to properly plan and conduct the restoration actions. Some direct and indirect parameters (allometric and plot vegetational/community characteristics) are shown in Table 5.

Table 5 - Some allometric and plot vegetational/community characteristics have been considered in the Nestos area to characterise plant community and species composition to plan the restoration actions foreseen in the LIFE PRIMED project.

Allometric parameters	Plot characteristics	Individual added parameters	Derived parameters per plot
Diameter at breast height (DBH, cm)	Slope (%)	The strain from climbing plants	Composition (plant number/species/ha)
Tree height (m)	Canopy density (%)	Insect infestation	Density (plants/ha)
Branching degree	Tree cover (%)	Logged tree tip.	Distribution of diametrical classes
	Shrub cover (%)		Basal area (m ² /ha)
	Herbaceous plant cover (%)		Amount of sunlight available to the regeneration as a function of the Basal area.

The hydraulic interventions aim at ensuring the proper water balance in the forest ecosystem by supplying a supplementary water resource during the driest periods. It is based on the interception of groundwater of the Nestos River. Ponds tend to dry through evaporation during extreme heating due to the presence of the upper clay layer. A system composed by six well-points can exploit groundwater with limited flow rates and maintain humidity in the topsoil with micro-irrigation systems, releasing water before or during possible droughts to meet the water needs (Figs. 6-7). The function of this system is to mitigate the aridity attributed to climate change affecting the site over the last decades and, along with the other C actions, to promote the conservation of Nestos wood (habitat 91M0) and the associated ecosystems, such as the Mediterranean temporary ponds.

Fig.6 Sketch of well point location and water distribution in the study area.

Fig.7 Sketch of the single well-point related to the project (left) and water distribution network with sprinklers (right).

The proposed forestry and hydraulic interventions represent the optimal option to deal with these problems and would substantially impact the entire system of forests and temporary ponds. The system represents an application of hydraulic methodologies in favour of natural ecosystems with low environmental impact: the water flow is limited; No fossil fuels are used, and the pumping system is powered by photovoltaic panels; Well points and pumping are completely underground; There are no excavation costs, with zero landfill disposal.

Landscape, environmental, ecological and socio-economic indicators for the Alta Murgia National Park (Southern Italy)

The Alta Murgia site, which is a SCI and Special Protection Area (SPA) with the code IT9120007, includes the Italian “Alta Murgia” National Park established in 2004. It lies in the Murgia geographical area (Apulia, southern Italy), with its headquarters in the town of Gravina in Puglia, and has an area of 677.39 square kilometers. The site is characterized by the presence of highly diverse unique ecosystems and also of endemic and threatened grassland species (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8 - Landscape of the Alta Murgia National Park, characterised also by reforestation activities mainly focussed on conifers (*Pinus halepensis*) well adapted to karst soils

The park is home to a variety of flora and fauna, including wild orchids, birds of prey, and mammals such as foxes and wild boars. The most common forest formations in the Alta Murgia national park consist of oak species, with *Q. pubescens* L. being of significant importance. Other oak species found in the region include *Q. ilex* L., *Q. cerris* L., *Q. coccifera* L., *Q. calliprinos* Webb, *Q. frainetto* Ten., and the rare *Quercus trojana* Webb. The undergrowth is characterized by species such as *Lonicera* sp., *Crataegus monogyna* Jacq., and numerous herbaceous and shrubs

including the *Peonia mascula* L. Mill., *Clematis flammula* L., *Rosa sempervirens* L., *Rosa canina* L., *Arum italicum* Mill., and *Cyclamen hederifolium* Aiton. Widespread artificial plantings of Aleppo pine are present, which were reforested over 50 years starting from 1930 and covered an area of approximately 25,000 hectares in the region's internal and coastal areas. The region's pine forests are mainly made up of *Pinus halepensis* Mill. and *Cupressus sempervirens* L., with an undergrowth of *Q. pubescens*, *Pistacia lentiscus* L., and *Phillyrea* sp. The steppe areas are characterized by herbaceous vegetation, including priority species such as *Stipa austroitalica* Martinowsky and numerous species of orchids belonging to the genera *Serapias*, *Orchis*, and *Ophrys*, including the recently discovered species called *Ophrys murgiana*. The natural pastures are characterized by arboreal-shrub vegetation, consisting of wild olive (*Olea europaea* var. *sylvestris* L.), almond (*Amygdalus communis* L.), marruca (*Paliurus spina christi* Mill.), medlar (*Mespilus germanica* L.), blackthorn (*Prunus spinosa* L.), pear (*Pyrus amygdaliformis*), wild almond (*Prunus webbii* Spach), hawthorn (*Crataegus monogyna* Jacq.), and rhamnus (*Rhamnus saxatilis* Jacq.). Over the years, the vegetation in the park has adapted itself to the constant changes of the climate and the geology of the area (Fig. 9). However, the wildlife in the national park has also suffered in the past few years due to hunting and extreme environmental changes. The park has faced several environmental problems, including degradation of the karst landscape, habitat fragmentation, a loss of natural habitats, and the spread of invasive plant species such as *Ailanthus altissima*. The intensive transformation experienced by the study site in the period 1973–2006, determined by the substantial land cover transition from pasture and permanent crops to cultivated areas. Further, the main karst features, such as doline and shallow valleys with flat bottoms, also locally known as lame, are partially or totally obliterated by agricultural practices. The Common Agricultural Policy (CAP) drove the transformation of grassland pastures into agricultural areas by stone (rock) graining (clearance), which also induced soil erosion and sediment deposition in aquifer, contamination. Illegal waste and toxic mud dumping on transformed areas caused heavy metal contamination of soils and aquifer systems. Increasing traditional legal and illegal mining activities, wind farms infrastructures, and below-average precipitation for many years have also contributed to the degradation of the site.

image © Delicious Italy

www.ambienteambientanti.com

Fig. 9 - The valleys of limestone outcrops are home to thriving tree and shrub communities (left), while the bauxite mines in Spinazzola are set to become a major attraction of Alta Murgia National Park (right).

Efforts have been made to address environmental threats that are caused by human activities, either directly or indirectly. To mitigate these threats, several projects have been undertaken in the area. Among these projects are LIFE Alta Murgia (LIFE12 BIO/IT/000213) and LIFE NEWLIFE4DRYLANDS (LIFE20 PRE/IT/000007), which aim to restore the structural and functional activities of ecosystems while minimizing the impact of human activity. These projects include a series of experimental field activities to achieve their goals. The LIFE Alta Murgia had as main objective the eradication of the invasive alien woody species *Ailanthus altissima* from the Alta Murgia National Park by innovative, eco-friendly and sustainable chemical strategy with the aim to: halt the loss of biodiversity; reduce the spread and negative impact of the most widespread invasive alien species of the Park; safeguard and improve the conservation status of the most important natural habitats and wild species in the Alta Murgia National Park, protected under the EC Habitat and Wild Birds Directives, and threatened by the presence of *Ailanthus altissima*; sustain chemical strategy to eradicate and control *A. altissima* that could increase efficacy and minimize herbicide use and dispersal. The main activities concerned: Census, mapping and monitoring of the invasive species *A. altissima* in the park; Technical personnel training; Control of invasive trees by eco-friendly methods and protocol issue; Trunk's recovery and disposal; Evaluation of the impact of the project actions. A detailed technical procedure has been written in the Project's Final technical report. The systemic herbicide used (glyphosate), applied at low volume directly into the stems, proved to be effective for the control of *Ailanthus*. Its impact on

the local flora was null. Indeed, during the growing season following the treatment, the spontaneous vegetation grew properly next to the treated plants. The optimal period for treatments was late summer. Depending on the level of infestation, after the first intervention, if new re-sprouts grew, one or more completion treatments were necessary to eradicate the species. Monitoring over time was necessary. All these features could be useful for the Nestos River site, where *Amorpha fruticosa* and *Acer negundo* represent a particularly important invasive plants for the area, negatively affecting the compositional plant species of both riparian and grassland plant communities. Finally, the LIFE Alta Murgia project allowed to create of a detailed map of the presence of *A. altissima* in the Alta Murgia National Park and census of 749 infestation areas. Fulfilment of a control strategy effective for *A. altissima* and other woody invasive species, based on environment friendly physical and chemical treatment techniques.

Furthermore, During the last three decades, this unique ecosystem has been exposed to high impacts and accelerated processes of habitat degradation, fragmentation, and biotic contamination (i.e., woody encroachment), both within and next to its borders. As a result of the combined pressures, ecosystems are threatened or even in danger of destruction. Hence, the following indicators, reported in Table 6, have been selected spanning a period over the last 30 years for trend in Land Cover and over the last 20 years for trend in phenology, map of the grassland habitat, burned areas, SOC evaluation and climate trend analysis. All these indicators should be used to better characterise the karst-conditioned habitats of the Alta Murgia.

Table 6 - A series of RS-based indicators used to investigate the functional state of the Alta Murgia site

SITE	INDICATORS	SENSOR	SPATIAL RESOLUTION (meters)	SPATIAL FRAME	TEMPORAL FRAME	VALIDATION GROUND DATA	NOTES
ALTA MURGIA	LAND COVER MAP (i.e. GRASSLANDS)	LANDSAT	30	NATURA 2K +5 km buffer	1990;2001;2004; 2011	Available ground data	Temporal framework according to Corine Land Cover products for comparison purposes. 2004: Institution National Park
		LANDSAT SENTINEL-2	30 - 10		2018		
		SENTINEL-2	10		2021		
	GRASSLAND HABITAT MAP	SENTINEL-2	10	Subset where ground data are available	2018;2014		
	BURNED AREAS COVER TREND	LANDSAT SENTINEL-2	30	NATURA 2K +5 km buffer	2000; 2021 Interannual times series	Available archives from State Forestry Service	
	PHENOLOGY TREND		10			Validation by field instruments or Arif database	
	VEGETATION SUFFERING ESTIMATION	MODIS PRISMA	MODIS 1000 Daily acquisition PRISMA 30 Monthly acquisition	Only for those LC classes for which ground data are available	2000; 2021 Interannual times series	Possible validation by soil chamber gas exchanges (2021-2022) and correlation with Primary Production	Possible super-resolution or pansharpened techniques for PRISMA data. • spring and autumn measures (2021-2022)- correlation with Primary Production
	SOIL ORGANIC COMPOUNDS	SENTINEL-2 PRISMA	10			2020	Available ground data (2020)
HISTORICAL CLIMATE ANALYSIS	Chelsa and ERA5 Land	1km (Chelsa) 9km (ERA5-Land)	NATURA 2K +5 km buffer	Daily stats 1981-2005 Hourly 1979-2021	Local weather stations		

Considering the karst nature of the Alta Murgia environmental system, the results conducted in China in the karst region of southwest China, which hosts one of the largest continuous karst phenomena in the world, are fascinating. A series of government initiatives have been carried out since 1999 to restore natural vegetation, prevent soil erosion and control rocky desertification. In particular, the study aimed to investigate the trend of net ecosystem productivity (NEP) in the karst region of southwest China during 2000-2018 and to analyze the relative contribution of multiple environmental factors (e.g., climate change, atmospheric CO₂ concentration, nitrogen deposition and land use change). The Community Land Model version 4.5 (CLM4.5) was used to simulate the temporal variation of net ecosystem productivity (NEP) and regional contribution in different karst regions. Finally, a series of simulation experiments were carried out to quantify the impacts of different factors on NEP trends. The study found that nearly half (46%) of the karst region's ecosystems showed a significant increase in net ecosystem productivity (NEP), with the majority of them located on plateaus, colliculus regions, peak cluster depression regions, and middle-upper hilly regions. The researchers also conducted simulation experiments, which suggested that the increase in NEP trend was largely caused by land use changes associated with ecological restoration projects (53%) and CO₂ fertilization (72%). Climate factors and nitrogen deposition had a minor negative effect. The NEP trend induced by land use change in the 100 pilot counties with the implementation of the rocky desertification control project was significantly higher than that in other karst areas. Additionally, the study found that restoration efforts invested in recovery had a significant impact on the NEP trend. Moderate and elevated levels of restoration efforts led to a larger increase in NEP (0.66 gC/m²/year and 0.48 gC/m²/year) compared to low efforts (0.22 gC/m²/year). These findings emphasized the importance of ecological restoration projects in enhancing terrestrial carbon sequestration in the karst region of southwest China and recommended a comprehensive evaluation of ecological restoration projects for decision-making.

Data The input data of CLM4.5 mainly include seven climate variables (i.e., air temperature, precipitation, relative humidity, downwelling longwave radiation, downwelling short-wave radiation, surface pressure, and wind speed), two atmospheric environment variables (i.e.,

atmospheric CO₂ concentration and nitrogen deposition), and other environment variables, such as plant function type, and dynamic land use and land cover change data. The atmospheric CO₂ concentration (1850–2015) with a spatial resolution of 1° comes from Mauna Loa Observatory (Lamarque et al., 2010). The atmospheric nitrogen deposition data (1980–2015) with a spatial resolution of 0.05° were calculated based on the atmospheric inorganic nitrogen wet deposition data proposed by Jia et al. (2019) and the dry and wet nitrogen deposition ratio developed by Yu et al. (2019). The plant functional type and dynamic land use and land cover changes data (1990–2015) with a spatial resolution of 0.05° were processed based on the land cover data of China (ChinaCover) produced by Wu et al. (2014) and climate variables (Wang et al., 2017) using the method reported in Bonan et al. (2018). The parameter values of the leaf carbon to nitrogen ratio for each plant functional type were revised against the inventory data (Tang et al., 2018). The Standardized Precipitation Index (SPI; Vicente-Serrano (2006)) data have been obtained by using monthly precipitation data. The SPI computed on shorter scales (e.g., 3 months) was used to find drought events. The drought events were extracted with SPI 3 data <-1.0, (Vicente-Serrano et al., 2014).

The increase in carbon sequestration in the karst region of southwest China has been proven to be associated with ecological restoration projects after 2000 (Brandt et al., 2018; Zhang X. et al., 2022). Results suggested that land use change was the second large contributor to the sustained carbon sequestration besides elevated atmospheric CO₂ concentration. To alleviate ecological degradation and improve regional poverty, the Chinese government has invested in a series of mitigation initiatives, which are aimed at converting farmlands and degraded lands into conservation or production forests and grasslands (Delang and Yuan, 2016). The land use change resulted in a significant increase in carbon sequestration by increasing the aboveground and underground carbon density (Hong et al., 2020) and the turnover of carbon storage (Chen and Tian, 2007). With the increase of forest coverage driven by ecological restoration projects, the average ratio of the ecosystem service index increased (Zhang M. et al., 2022). With the increase of ecological restoration projects efforts, the growth rate of vegetation cover and carbon density became faster (Lv et al., 2018; Tong et al., 2018). The land use change played a key role in stimulating the positive trend in NEP besides atmospheric

CO₂ concentration in this region, while climate and nitrogen deposition had relatively small negative contributions. Moreover, with the large-scale afforestation and cropland abandonment, a notable increase in NEP was found in the 100 pilot counties of rocky desertification control project, when compared with the other karst areas.

Essential Bibliography

Lv, Y., Zhang, L., Li, P., He, H., Ren, X., & Zhang, M. (2023). Ecological restoration projects enhanced terrestrial carbon sequestration in the karst region of Southwest China. *Frontiers in Ecology and Evolution*, 11, 1179608.

Lamarque, J. F., Bond, T. C., Eyring, V., Granier, C., Heil, A., Klimont, Z., ... & Van Vuuren, D. P. (2010). Historical (1850–2000) gridded anthropogenic and biomass burning emissions of reactive gases and aerosols: methodology and application. *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics*, 10(15), 7017–7039.

Jia, Y., Wang, Q., Zhu, J., Chen, Z., He, N., and Yu, G. (2019). A spatial and temporal dataset of atmospheric inorganic nitrogen wet deposition in China (1996–2015). *China Sci. Data*. 4, 1–10.

Yu, G., Jia, Y., He, N., Zhu, J., Chen, Z., Wang, Q., et al. (2019). Stabilization of atmospheric nitrogen deposition in China over the past decade. *Nat. Geosci.* 12, 424–429. doi: 10.1038/s41561-019-0352-4

Wu, B., Yuan, Q., Yan, C., Wang, Z., Yu, X., Li, A., et al. (2014). Land cover changes of China from 2000 to 2010. *Quat Sci* 34, 723–731.

Wang, J., Wang, J., Ye, H., Liu, Y., and He, H. (2017). An interpolated temperature and precipitation dataset at 1-km grid resolution in China (2000–2012). *China Sci. Data*. 2, 73–80. doi: 10.11922/csdata.170.2016.0112

Bonan, G. B., Levis, S., Kergoat, L., and Oleson, K. W. (2018). Landscapes as patches of plant functional types: an integrating concept for climate and ecosystem models. *Global Biogeochem Cycles* 16, 5-1–5-23. doi: 10.1029/2000GB001360

Tang, Z., Xu, W., Zhou, G., Bai, Y., Li, J., Tang, X., et al. (2018). Patterns of plant carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus concentration in relation to productivity in China's terrestrial ecosystems. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 115, 4033–4038. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1700295114

Vicente-Serrano, S. (2006). Differences in spatial patterns of drought on different time scales: an analysis of the Iberian Peninsula. *Water Resour. Manag.* 20, 37–60. doi: 10.1007/s11269-006-2974-8

Vicente-Serrano, S. M., Julio Camarero, J., and Azorin-Molina, C. (2014). Diverse responses of forest growth to drought time-scales in the northern hemisphere. *Glob. Ecol. Biogeogr.* 23, 1019–1030. doi: 10.1111/geb.12183

Brandt, M., Yue, Y., Wigneron, J. P., Tong, X., Tian, F., Jepsen, M. R., et al. (2018). Satellite-observed major greening and biomass increase in South China karst during recent decade. *Earth's Future* 6, 1017–1028. doi: 10.1029/2018EF000890

Zhang, M., Zhang, L., He, H., Ren, X., Lv, Y., and Chang, Q. (2022). Improvement of ecosystem quality in National key Ecological Function Zones in China during 2000–2015. *J. Environ. Manag.* 324:116406. doi: 10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.116406

Delang, C. O., and Yuan, Z. (2016). *China's Grain for Green Program*. New York, United States: Springer International.

Chen, G., and Tian, H. (2007). Land use/cover change effects on carbon cycling in terrestrial ecosystems. *Chin. J. Plant Ecol.* 31, 189–204. doi: 10.17521/cjpe.2007.0024

Hong, S., Yin, G., Piao, S., Dybzinski, R., Cong, N., Li, X., et al. (2020). Divergent responses of soil organic carbon to afforestation. *Nat. Sustain.* 3, 694–700. doi: 10.1038/s41893-020-0557-y

Tong, X., Brandt, M., Yue, Y., Horion, S., Wang, K., Keersmaecker, W. D., et al. (2018). Increased vegetation growth and carbon stock in China karst via ecological engineering. *Nat. Sustain.* 1, 44–50. doi: 10.1038/s41893-017-0004-x

Landscape, environmental, ecological and socio-economic indicators for the El Bruc site (North/Western Spain) and the Tifaracàs site (Canary Islands, Spain)

El Bruc site is 700 ha wide, located at an elevation of 450-500 m corresponding mainly to private properties. Its climate is Mediterranean, with a precipitation average of 666 mm/y, 46 average days of rain, and more than 3 dry months. This area went under a natural fire in 2015 which burnt more than 1000 ha, and formerly in 1986, thus it presents a high level of degradation: soil erosion and land abandonment (Fig. 10a and Tab.7). However, it represents a protection and connection corridor for the Montserrat Roques Blanques-riu Llobregat SCI (code ES5110012), an emblematic area with a high touristic, aesthetic and ecologic value.

Fig. 10 – a) El Bruc site. Land degradation and soil erosion are evident, but a powerful secondary ecological succession is occurring. Under these environmental conditions, a restoration plan included the afforestation with a mosaic of agricultural and forest species using the Cocoon Ecotechnology.

Tifaracàs site is a desertified area located in the municipality of Artenara, on the island of Gran Canaria. It is located within the El Nublo Rural Park, which in turn forms part of the Gran Canaria Biosphere Reserve. The area is classified as a Site of Community Interest (SCI) and Special Area of Conservation (SAC), included in the Natura 2000 Network. Although the area has a high risk of desertification, there is vegetation typical of the arid and semi-arid environments of the

island, with a predominance of herbaceous species, although with a very low cover. Within the framework of the LIFE The Green Link project (LIFE15 CCA / SE / 125), some 4000 seedlings of native forest species, trees, and shrubs, were planted using the “Cocoon” system. The planting aims to reverse the desertification processes and improve the ecological connectivity of the adjacent Canary Island pine forests. The area is severely affected by desertification processes, which are aggravated by reduced rainfall, recurrent forest fires, and herbivory caused by the abundant presence of feral goats (Fig. 10b). Average annual rainfall is below 200 mm, although in recent years it has not exceeded 100 mm. In recent years, dry periods without rain have lasted more than 10 months, making it very difficult to reforest the area in an attempt to establish a vegetation cover to protect the soil from erosion. Although the high stoniness of the soil means that it is not particularly vulnerable to erosion, the low vegetation cover, the steep slope of the hillsides, and the torrential rains favour erosion processes. These processes lead to the loss of fertile soil, making it even more difficult to establish vegetation cover.

Fig. 10 – b) Semi-arid landscape of the Tifaracàs site showing outcropping rocks as a result of a high rate of soil degradation.

Table 7 – Soil properties in the El Bruc and Tifaracàs sites

Site	Texture	CaCO3 (%)	SOM (%)	CEC (cmol kg ⁻¹)	pH water (1:2,5 w/v)	pH water (saturated paste)	SOC stock (T/ha)
El Bruc	Clayey sandy	28.74±11.33	3.28±1.65	14.18 ± 3.39	8.45 ± 0.38	7.72 ± 4.03	58.03±26.18
Tifaracàs	Clay	6.5 ± 3.0	43.7 ± 3.4	7.70 ± 0.23	0.95 ± 0.13	1.62 ± 0.35	12.99 ± 3.81

The following Tables 8 (El Bruc) and 9 (Tifaracàs) show indices and sub-indicators of the functional state of the forest and land degradation and desertification, also according to the SDG 15.3.1 indicators of the UNCCD, fully explained in the Deliverable A2.1 "Indicators for the evaluation of restoration actions to combat degradation/desertification".

Table 8 - Indices and sub-indicators were selected for the El Bruc study site.

Site	Sub-indicators		Sensor	Spatial resolution (m)	Spatial frame	Temporal frame
El Bruc	BURN SEVERITY MAP		Landsat	30	4 sub-areas within N2K	2015
			Sentinel-2	10		
	LAND COVER MAP		Landsat	30		1987; 1992; 1997; 2002; 2007; 2012
			Sentinel-2	10		2017; 2021
	PRIMARY PRODUCTIVITY	VEGETATION PHENOLOGY INDEX (PPI)	Sentinel-2	10		2017-2020
SOC		Landsat/Sentinel2	10	2007-2017		
	STANDARDISED PRECIPITATION EVAPOTRANSPIRATION INDEX (SPEI)		Meteorological stations			1950-2019

Table 9 - Indices and sub-indicators were selected for the Tifaracàs study site.

Site	Sub-indicators		Sensor	Spatial resolution (m)	Spatial frame	Temporal frame
	BURN SEVERITY MAP		Sentinel-2	10		2019
	LAND COVER MAP		Landsat	30	4 sub-areas	2005; 2011; 2014
			Sentinel-2	10		2016; 2021

Tifaracas	PRIMARY PRODUCTIVITY	VEGETATION PHENOLOGY INDEX (PPI)	Sentinel-2	10	within N2K	2017-2020
	SOC		Landsat/Sentinel2	10; 30		2005-2021

Despite efforts to reforest the Mediterranean region, many reforestation projects have been unsuccessful due to slow growth rates and high mortality rates of planted seedlings. Droughts lasting between 3 and 5 months, nutrient limitations, and shallow soils with low water holding capacity are some of the challenges faced during reforestation efforts. Even with regular irrigation, the survival rate of many species is no more than 50%, and root systems with inadequate irrigation do not penetrate deep enough into the soil, limiting plant establishment. Nature-based solutions can be used to address environmental problems and improve reforestation projects. These solutions involve protecting, managing, and sustainably restoring natural ecosystems, while also providing benefits to society and biodiversity. This umbrella concept covers a range of different approaches, including ecotechnologies designed to support restoration projects and plantings. In this area have been implemented two LIFE projects: The Green Link (*Restore desertified areas with an innovative tree growing method across the Mediterranean border to increase resilience*; LIFE15 CA/ES/000125) and Nieblas (*Reforestation & Climate Change Mitigation: tests, evaluation, and transfer of innovative methods based on fog collection*; LIFE19 CCM/ES/001199), co-funded by the EU LIFE program. Here, a technology recognised as Cocoon™, a water-saving ecotechnology that supports plantings in drylands has been tested and integrated with other NbSs. Briefly, this eco-technology is made of paper pulp and resembles the buried clay pot used in ancient times to slowly seep water into the subsurface and support plant growth while restricting evaporation losses (Fig. 11). The Cocoon has been previously tested in the Mediterranean basin, Canary Islands, and Lower Rio Grande Valley of South Texas, among other places, with promising results.

Fig. 11 - Scheme of the Cocoon™ components. From the Final Report of GreenLink Life Project.

The planting areas are situated in the Municipality of El Bruc - adjacent to the Montserrat Mountains, and precisely 10 km east of Igualada and 15 km west of Terrassa. In August 2015, a massive fire devastated an area of roughly 1,300 hectares, which had already been partially burned in 1986, resulting in a highly degraded region. This area is a unique geological formation and an emblematic geographical area of Catalonia. The challenge of the LIFE Green Link project was to reforest a portion of this heavily damaged area that suffers from prolonged periods of drought in the summer.

In Tifaracàs, the plantation area is in the Natural Park "Tamadaba" (SAC ES0000111 and SPA ES0000346), which is included in the Gran Canaria Biosphere Reserve and the European Natura 2000 network. The plantation covers an area surface of 12 ha, owned by the Cabildo de Gran Canaria. It has a semi-arid warm climate with hot summers (maximum 28.6 °C), and mild winters (14.3 °C), with some minimum rainfall that does not exceed 177 mm/year and often falls as heavy rains. The dry period lasts about 10 months. The goal of the trials was to increase the connectivity between the green spaces in the protected zone and improve eroded soils.

The LIFE Green Link proposal was to use adaptive and economically viable species, such as olives and oak trees inoculated with truffles, to create more diverse, multi-species areas of resilient and productive forests. In particular, several monitoring parameters have been taken in

consideration: Vigour, Seedling growth, Cocoon degradation, Vegetation structure, Composition of vegetation (biodiversity), Adjacent vegetation, and Fauna.

Results proved that in El Bruc plantation were observed differences regarding mortality and the number of healthy plants, while the affected plants were kept in similar percentages. Mortality in control seedlings was 67%, higher than in cocoon specimens, where it was reduced to 43%. On the contrary, the percentage of healthy plants increased in individuals with Cocoon up to 44%, while in control seedlings it only reached 25% of the total (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12 – Healthy and mortality percentages observed in El Bruc test site between controls and Cocoon-based plots. (From Action D1. Monitoring and project performance indicators, LIFE Green Link - LIFE 15/CCA/ES/125).

In general, the plants grown with Cocoon showed greater growth and healthier conditions compared to the control group planted directly on the ground. The data unequivocally shows that there has been a significant increase in the cover of both herbaceous and woody plants in all three sampling areas. This increase in plant cover has led to a marked increase in species diversity. The average height of both types of vegetation has also increased significantly, further emphasizing the extent of the change. The sampling campaigns showed a remarkable increase in wildlife. The most observed wildlife were insects like wasps, bees, and butterflies, as well as arachnids. Small vertebrates like reptiles were also making an appearance. Traces of wild boars, roe deer, rabbits, and dogs have also been detected. Moreover, the Cocoon was teeming with a diverse range of invertebrates that occupied the central hole, protector, and bowl, as well as the space between the Cocoon and the ground. The area was also home to many wasp nests,

spiders, opilions, and even some scorpions. The wildlife population has also caused some damage, in El Bruc field trials; Wild boars, roe deer, and feral goats have been responsible for the damages.

In the plantation carried out in Tifaracás, high mortality rates were observed in all treatments (Fig. 13). However, it stands out that, unlike in the El Bruc site, the lowest mortality occurs in the control seedlings (62%). The controls also have the highest proportion of healthy seedlings, although the differences with the Cocoon treatment decrease over time.

Fig. 13 - distribution of the monitored seedlings planted in Tifaracás (Gran Canaria), according to their physiological state in May-June 2019. (From Action D1. Monitoring and project performance indicators, LIFE Green Link - LIFE 15/CCA/ES/125).

In spite that there are no notable differences between the other treatments with Cocoon, the control one has better survival and a higher percentage of healthy plants. General results in Tifaracás are heavily conditioned by pine plantations, where controls were watered one time during the summer of 2017, for which they have higher survival rates. For the rest of the species, this trend changes, and better survival rates were observed in seedlings with Cocoon than in controls (Figure 13). *Pistacia Atlantica* has high mortality rates in both treatments, but survival was higher in Cocoons due to a higher percentage of severely affected seedlings. Mortality is also high in *Juniperus turbinata*, being 100% in controls and close to 80% in plants with Cocoon. The best survival results were obtained with *Olea europaea* with a mortality that did not reach 25% of the specimens and a high percentage of healthy seedlings, close to 50%. In controls, mortality was higher (32%) and the number of affected plants increased.

Generally, Cocoon technology for reforestation proved to be useful in a wide range of arid and semi-arid conditions. In general, conventional plantations showed higher mortalities and lower vigour rates than plantations using this technology. The direct and indirect water supply, the mitigation of plant competition around the seedling, the reduction of evapotranspiration, and the micro-catchment effect create a very suitable set of conditions for the improvement of the physiological state of plants, which increase their survival. Overall, these findings are a testament to the success of the conservation efforts in the area, to preserve the natural habitat and ensure a safe environment for both humans and wildlife.

Regarding assisted migration tests, the case of *Quercus ilex ssp ballota* is especially remarkable. *Ballota* subspecies worked very well in El Bruc, with a survival greater than 60% in the Cocoons, and even statistically significant differences for growth being higher in the seedlings with the Cocoon device. This olm oak plantation could be considered an example of adaptive restoration to climate change (Lhumeau and Cordero, 2012; Pramova et al., 2019), as it is an indigenous subspecies of southern Spain and northwestern Africa, planted at higher latitudes, simulating the displacement that this species could suffer with climate change, through the assisted migration mechanism (Sansilvestri et al., 2016; Schwartz et al., 2012).

The LIFE Nieblas project has several aims to counteract land degradation and desertification processes such as reforesting degraded areas with native plants using water from the different types of water collectors and different methods of irrigation; to increase the vegetation coverage, thus achieving greater water filtration, decrease runoff, and increase the soil water absorption capacity. Hence, increasing the environmental quality of the area (increasing biodiversity and reducing carbon footprint); to compare the efficiency of all water collectors and irrigation systems. 100% of the water needed will be provided by the water collectors.

The main acting zones for this project have been planned for Gran Canaria and Portugal. The former area is located in Barranco de la Virgen, Valleseco in Gran Canaria with an area comprising some 35.8ha. The selected landscape is partially found under a Special Area of Conservation (ZEC ES7010038 from its Spanish acronym) being part of the Natura 2000 Network. The area is found with extremely low vegetation cover, and some sporadic growth of alien species (i.e., fern, bramble, chestnut trees) rather than its natural xeric Laurisilva forest.

Leaving this area to self-develop, will not only lead to higher runoff rates but also to water cycle disruptions (including underground water systems) posing a higher risk for the spread of wildfire. Out of the 20,000 new trees to be planted in Gran Canaria, almost 9,000 have already been planted. Species include *Erica arborea*, *Laurus novocanariensis* and *Ilex canariensis* (along eight other species proper from this landscape). Portugal, on the other hand, follows the same procedures implemented in Gran Canaria. The reforestation activities have been performed at two sites; Carregal Do Sal (6ha within a Site of Community Importance, SCI) and Vouzela (4ha) classified natural landscape where Life Nieblas aims to restore an oak forest (i.e. *Quercus ruber*, *Quercus pyrenaica*). At these two locations, the plan is to plant 5,000 trees of which 2,500 have already been planted.

Four reforestation methods were implemented in the development of this project; Traditional reforestation (control groups) and three additional innovative methods that offered a more efficient and cleaner solution to reforestation activities: **Cocoons** (a biodegradable, self-contained nurturing system which was developed by a previous project 'LIFE Green Link'; **Individual Fog Water Collectors (IFWC)** wind and herbivores protection mesh for individual plants that function as atmospheric humidity collectors; **Autonomous Discharge System (AFDS)**. This last one is only taking place in Gran Canaria due to the testing phase of the prototype and transport logistics at present.

At Life Nieblas, activities were not only concerned with habitat restoration actions but also contributed to the mitigation of the effects of climate change and the reduction of CO₂e emissions. Therefore, 'innovative Fog Water Collectors (i-FWC)' have been designed and built as an environmentally clean method of water collection for reforestation works in areas of difficult accessibility.

Both testing areas have been heavily affected by wildfires between the years 2014 and 2019, and there has been no effort to restore them since then. Currently, the ecological condition of these sites is characterized by the first growth of shrubs and wildflowers. Moreover, these areas are facing various common pressures such as unselective logging, commercial woodland plantations, excessive water extraction, and anthropogenic influences.

A Fog Water Collector (FWC) must comply with certain characteristics that will not only make it efficient at collecting water, cheap to build, and easy to install but also resistant to the passing of time and the climatic stress that a foggy, humid, and windy environment can put over this structure (Fig. 14). In this project two types of FWCs are tested; a traditional (pre-existing model) and an innovative design (developed by Life Nieblas engineers).

Fig. 14 – Components of a Fog Water Collector (FWC). From a report about Action C.2: Execution of traditional and innovative reforestation. Methods employed. LIFE Nieblas project.

Over the course of the first year of data collection, it was seen a clear seasonal pattern in water collection. Throughout the data set, there was a significant decrease in water capture during the summer months, which is the driest season in The Canary Islands. In contrast, it was noticed

a larger amount of water collection between November 2021 and March 2022, amounting to approximately 45000 L. A similar pattern was in the same period for 2022/23. However, when the data was compared from 2022, a much lower expected seasonal water collection tendency was observed than in 2021. It was believed that these differences could be affected by yearly meteorological variations.

Ground conditioning is a crucial aspect of Life Nieblas's development at the field level. It involves a comprehensive process that starts with an assessment of the field by technicians, followed by field clearing, construction conditioning, repurposing, installation of safety measures, distribution of water storage, and the associated pipeline network. Planning reforestation methodologies and implementing them is also an essential part of this process. The project layer of fieldwork connects partners with all their technical, scientific, and engineering desk and fieldwork. This holistic approach ensures that any issues encountered during the project are identified and addressed promptly, and solutions are planned to overcome challenges. The focus of this project is mainly to restore the xeric Laurisilva forest (Fig. 15) that once inhabited this part of the Gran Canaria Island, helping in natural water cycle restoration and endemic species spreading (flora and fauna).

Fig. 15 - Anaga Massive, one of the most important Laurisilva woodlands in The Canary Islands.

Field activities, such as clearing dead plants, debris, and waste, and preparing sites for housing 5000L tanks and Fog Water Collectors, require the presence of qualified personnel working in close synergy with project technicians. This organization is an integral part of the prospects for success of the LIFE Niebles project, which is based on Nature-based Solutions. It is also crucial for the LIFE PRIMED project, which aims to create a hydraulic structure to support plant growth during the summer periods of water scarcity and elevated temperatures. Furthermore, soil sampling tasks were performed. Such analyses are relevant to understanding what soil typologies we find at the reforestation sites, their composition differences, and how they change towards the end of the project, expecting an improvement in soil quality.

The reforested areas have been measured based on various parameters such as the number of seedlings planted, identification of seedlings, plant growth, and the total area reforested. The monitoring activities included four reforestation methodologies:

- a) Traditional reforestation: This will work as a control group, following traditional reforestation methodologies (Fig. 16A).
- b) Cocoon: This is a self-sustaining and biodegradable container that will provide water to each seedling independently in an on-demand manner. This system will also protect the plants against little herbivores and wind (Fig. 16B).
- c) Individual Fog Collectors (IFC): These are conventional protective metal meshes that have the capability of collecting atmospheric humidity in the condensation process that occurs under drastic changes in temperature. It provides a source of water to every seedling (Fig. 16C).
- d) Autonomous Fluid Discharge System (AFDS): This system consists of a device that can store water in a discontinuous manner until the discharge level is reached. This guarantees a steady irrigation rate to the plotted area simultaneously and equally (Fig. 16D).

Fig. 16 - The four reforestation methodologies tested in Life-Nieblas (from the Mid-term Report of the LIFE Nieblas project)

Interestingly, the following text outlines the various monitoring protocols employed to evaluate the *impact of the Life-Nieblas project on both the environment and society*. The project's effect is assessed in terms of job creation and its benefits. a) Direct Jobs Generated: This section will detail the personnel hired directly for the project, such as Specialised Field Workers. The number of employees hired will have a contract for the duration of the project, ensuring employment for at least 4 years from the beginning of the contract. b) Directly Affected Jobs: All permanent pre-existing beneficiaries' employees who give timesheets under the Life-Nieblas project are accounted for under this section. These employees work part-time on the project, and include researchers, project directors, coordinators, financial technicians, etc. c) Indirectly Affected Jobs: The project's execution has an indirect impact on different departments such as

IT, HR, H&S, Finance, etc. These employees are accounted for as indirectly affected. d) External Assistance: This part measures the amount of outsourcing done directly by the project when the beneficiaries were not capable or did not have the resources to perform certain tasks. e) Replication Impact: This parameter measures how many replication projects were achieved by Life Nieblas and what participation they received from stakeholders. f) International Days: Entrepreneurship is encouraged and engaged during the event by involving different companies from sectors related to the topics revolving Life Nieblas. The number of projects, and investigations presented, and the number of people and entities taking part will be measured during the International Days on Climate Change. g) Economic Impact: This parameter is developed with the upcoming organization of the International Days. h) Public Outreach: The number of farmers, workers, students, and participants of various events is measured independently to assess the project's extent of impact on the public.

Essential Bibliography

Lhumeau, A., Cordero, D. (2012). Adaptación basada en Ecosistemas: una respuesta al cambio climático. Quito, Ecuador.

Pramova, E., Locatelli, B., Djoudi, H., Lavorel, S., Colloff, M., Martius, C. (2019). Para adaptar la restauración de la tierra a un clima cambiante: aceptemos lo que sabemos y lo que no. CIFOR Infobrief 272

Sansilvestri, R., Frascaria-Lacoste, N., Fernández-Manjarrés, J. (2016). One option, two countries, several strategies: subjacent mechanisms of assisted migration implementation in Canada and France. *Restoration Ecology* 24, 4, 489–498.

Schwartz, M.W., Jessica, J., Jason, M.M., Sax, D.F., Borevitz, J., Brennan, J., et al. (2012). Managed relocation: integrating the scientific, regulatory, and ethical challenges. *Bioscience* 62, 732–743

Landscape, environmental, ecological and socio-economic indicators for the Asterousia Mountains (Crete, Southern Greece)

The Asterousia Mt. Range, although considered of low productivity due to its rocky and sloppy terrain covered by a thin soil superlayer, has been inhabited, grazed, cultivated, and has sustained human communities since ancient times. The relatively low vegetation cover typical of the southeast Mediterranean, coupled with long dry summers and strong winter rainfalls which are intensified by the climatic deregulation of our times and multidimensional human pressures, have resulted in elevated risk of land degradation and desertification. In recent decades the Asterousia Mt. Range has seen a widespread change in land uses driven mainly by the abandonment of traditional cultivation on drywall terraces, the expansion of road networks and infrastructure serving tourism development and restoration ecological services (RES) projects. Another crucial change has been the overgrazing of virtually all grasslands due to the steep increase of livestock numbers and the abandonment of the traditional extensive animal farming model driven by the current CAP subsidies policy. These human pressures coupled with the effects of climate deregulation contribute to the increase of soil loss, erosion, and salinization resulting in the degradation of productive, arable land, decline of vegetation cover, loss of biodiversity and its functioning, habitat, and landscape modification, all of which eventually threaten Asterousia with desertification (Fig. 17). The inclusion of the Asterousia mountain range in the "Man and the Biosphere Programme" demonstrates the UNESCO's support of the Programme, acknowledging that the Asterousia, spanning 367 square kilometers, including the coastal and marine areas of the South Cretan Sea, represents a valuable ecosystem and community that must be preserved. The Biosphere Program's goal is to promote repopulation, ecotourism, production, and manufacturing in the Asterousia region, with a focus on sustainability. The management plan includes initiatives such as the planting of productive carob trees, the reduction of the goat population, and the management of marine litter. The goal is to protect the environment and its cultural elements while also strengthening the community.

Fig. 18 - A series of landscapes concerning the Asterousia Mountains, which highlight different land uses that occurred in the time in relation to the principal agronomical and farm activities.

The key pressures and main land degradation processes affecting the study area are:

- a) decline in vegetation cover/biomass and overgrazing resulting from the increase of livestock numbers;
- b) landscape modification, soil erosion, and soil organic matter decline due to anthropogenic interventions such as installation of new olive groves and greenhouses, opening of new roads, expansion of coastal tourism settlements, installation of Renewable Energy Sources facilities;
- c) accidental or intentional (for scrubland clearance) wildfires;
- d) hydrological modification;
- e) soil salinization due to overexploitation of aquifers.

Points (a) and (b) are crucial and have been the focus of several studies and proposals aimed at reducing their impact and causes. The study conducted by Kairis et al. (2015) shows that land management practices have a significant effect on soil erosion, water conservation, and

desertification risk. Sustainable grazing practices contribute to preserving a moderate annual vegetation cover, which in turn reduces runoff, sediment yield, and soil water loss through evapotranspiration (Carmona et al., 2013). Plant cover is a key factor in controlling water runoff and sediment loss, as confirmed by earlier research conducted in various environmental conditions (Francis and Thornes, 1990; Dunjo et al., 2004; Marques et al., 2007). Sustainable grazing is an effective measure to protect grazing land from soil erosion (Bernués et al., 2011). Interestingly, soil erosion rates were found to be lower under sustainable grazing than overgrazing, especially during intense rainfall events (Gómez et al., 2009). Sharma et al. (1997) stated that soil erosion rates during intense rainfall events can increase by 5 to 41 times in dry regions due to overgrazing. Soil erosion measurements carried out in grazing land in Greece and Spain (Kosmas et al., 1997) have shown that water runoff and sediment loss decrease with rainfall as long as precipitation exceeds 280-300 mm per year. With annual precipitation falling below this threshold, erosion decreases with climate aridity. To mitigate land degradation under climate change scenarios in grazing land, preserving vegetation cover at the plot scale is recommended (Stefanakis et al., 2007).

Papanastasis (1998) reported that overgrazing is probably the most crucial factor of land degradation in several Greek regions. Grazing land in Greece covers more than 40% of the total surface of the country (Zervas, 1998). As in other parts of Greece, grazing constitutes an ancient tradition in Crete as it has been practiced for more than 10 thousand years since the Neolithic times (Tsiourlis et al., 1998). The ability of the grazing animals to utilize the poor natural vegetation has led to the generation of low-requirements animal breeds. According to the Greek Statistical Service, the number of grazing animals (sheep and goats) on the island of Crete has increased from 0.78 to 1.01 million in the period 1960–1980 to 1.56–2.51 million in the period 1980–2010. The present stocking rate is much higher than the pasture carrying capacity (about 0.65 million) leading to overgrazing (Hadjigeorgiou et al., 2002). Papanastasis *et al.* (2017) have concluded that moderating grazing pressure rather than completely banning livestock grazing can contribute to the restoration of degraded rangelands.

Grazing management practices based on livestock density below the sustainable stocking rate can be applied to the study region and similar socioeconomic contexts in Southern Europe. This management type could be supported by local farmers in the future, given variations in land

prices, agricultural markets, rural depopulation, and changes in climate and land use (Bernués et al., 2011). Furthermore, the preservation of high-quality pastureland should be implemented through the right policies in Mediterranean areas sensitive to desertification (Peco et al., 2006). As indirect measures to mitigate land degradation, environmental policies should also promote greater awareness of the environmental risks associated with overgrazing, with a focus on erosion and soil fertility. Studies conducted with the participation of farmers may stimulate environmental awareness in rural communities exposed to desertification risk.

It is important to highlight that methodologies allowing the identification of sensitive areas to desertification have already been applied in several studies (Rubio & Bochet; 1998; Thornes, 2004; Simeonakis et al., 2007). Among them, the ESA (Environmental Sensitive Area) methodology, developed in the context of the EU-funded research project MEDALUS (Mediterranean Desertification and Land Use), appears to be the most widely applied in southern Europe and elsewhere (Ali & El Baroudy, 2008; Farajzabeh & Egbal, 2004; Salvati & Bajocco, 2011) due to model simplicity and flexibility in the use of available/relevant indicators (Kosmas et al., 1999; Basso et al, 2000). The procedure is based on the assessment of physical characteristics of the land such as soils, climate, and vegetation. Management characteristics such as land use type, intensity in the use of land, and policies are included to stress the importance of human-induced desertification. The ESA methodology has been validated at both local and regional scales in several testing areas of southern Europe (Portugal, Spain, Italy, and Greece) under different environmental conditions (Brandt et al., 2005; Brandt & Geeson, 2015). As Kosmas and co-workers reported (2015), sustainable grazing was a long-established practice in Asterousia, as in other Mediterranean marginal areas, as it was the only way of securing the future of a household. Land resources enabling grazing were the major assets of the households that provided the means for living. Grazing practices and livelihoods in general, as practiced in the early 1950s, are considered fairly sustainable concerning the protection of land resources from erosion and desertification. The stocking rate during the early 1950s was lower than 0.6 animals per hectare with rangeland stocking carrying capacity amounting to one animal per hectare. Economic and technological changes during the next “traditional-husbandry state” period (1950–mid-1980s) provided the alternative of increasing production to increase income, an option that led to intensive grazing (stocking rate 0.9–1.6 animals per

hectare) with subsequent degradation of the land. The reduced land productivity in turn led to an increased dependence on purchased fodder, paving the way for the widespread decoupling of production from land productivity that occurred in the following period.

The following Table 10 shows the main indices and sub-indicators of the functional state of the forest and land degradation and desertification, also according to the SDG 15.3.1 indicators of the UNCCD, fully explained in the Deliverable A2.1 “Indicators for the evaluation of restoration actions to combat degradation/desertification”.

Table 10. Indices and sub-indicators selected for the Asterousia study site.

Site	Sub-indicators	Sensor	Spatial resolution (m)	Spatial frame	Temporal frame	
Asterousia	LAND COVER MAP* BURN SEVERITY MAP*	Landsat	30	4 sub-areas within N2K	2000; 2005; 2010	
		Sentinel-2	10		2017; 2021	
	PRIMARY PRODUCTIVITY	VEGETATION PHENOLOGY INDEX (NDVI)	Modis		250	2000-2021
	SOIL SALINITY INDICES*		Sentinel-2		10	2017; 2021

Essential Bibliography

Ali, R.R.; El Baroudy, A.A. (2008). Use of GIS in mapping the environmental sensitivity to desertification in Wadi El Natrun depression, Egypt. *Aust. J. Basic Appl. Sci.* 2, 157–164.

Basso, F.; Bove, E.; Dumontet, S.; Ferrara, A.; Pisante, M.; Quaranta, G. (2000). Evaluating environmental sensitivity at the basin scale through the use of geographic information systems and remotely sensed data: An example covering the Agri basin—Southern Italy. *Catena* 40, 19–35

Bernués, A., R. Ruiz, A. Olaizola, D. Villalba, and I. Casasús (2011). Sustainability of pasture-based livestock farming systems in the European Mediterranean context: Synergies and trade-offs. *Livestock Science* 139: 44–57.

Brandt, J., & Geeson, N. (2015). Desertification indicator system for Mediterranean Europe: Science, stakeholders and public dissemination of research results. *Monitoring and Modelling Dynamic Environments: (A Festschrift in Memory of Professor John B. Thornes)*, 121-137. Access on 29/01/2024; https://web.archive.org/web/20190819055247id_/http://taurus.gg.bg.ut.ee:80/erasmusip/2011_Cagliari/materials/01_pre_learning/general/DESERTIFICATION%20INDICATOR%20SYSTEM.pdf

Brandt, J., Geeson, N., & Zucca, C. (2005). Desertification indicator system for Mediterranean Europe (DIS4ME). In *Proceedings of the AID-CCD International Workshop: Local & Regional Desertification Indicators in a Global Perspective*. Beijing, China, Enne G. and Yeroyanni M.(eds) (pp. 16-18).

Carmona, C. P., A. Röder, F. M. Azcárate, and B. Peco (2013). Grazing management or physiography? Factors controlling vegetation recovery in Mediterranean grasslands. *Ecological Modelling* 251: 73–84.

Dunjo, G., G. Pardini, and M. Gispert (2004). The role of land use–land cover on runoff generation and sediment yield at a microplot scale, in a small Mediterranean catchment. *Journal of Arid Environment* 57: 99–116.

Farajzabeh, M.; Egbal, M.N. (2007). Evaluation of MEDALUS model for Desertification Hazard Zonation using GIS; study area: Iyzad Khast Plain, Iran. *Pak. J. Biol. Sci.* 10, 2622–2630.

Francis, C. F., and J. B. Thornes (1990). Runoff hydrographs from three Mediterranean vegetation covers; In J. B. Thornes ed., *Vegetation and erosion*. Wiley, Chichester, pp. 363–385.

Gómez, J. A., T. A. Sobrinho, J. V. Giráldez, and E. Fereres (2009). Soil management effects on runoff, erosion and soil properties in an olive grove of Southern Spain. *Soil and Tillage Research* 102: 5–13.

Hadjigeorgiou, I.; Vallerand, F.; Tsimpoukas, K.; Zervas, G. (2002). The socio-economics of sheep and goat farming in Greece and the implications for future rural development. *Opt. Méditerr. Sér. B*, 39, 83–93.

Kairis, O., Karavitis, C., Salvati, L., Kounalaki, A., & Kosmas, K. (2015). Exploring the impact of overgrazing on soil erosion and land degradation in a dry Mediterranean agro-forest landscape (Crete, Greece). *Arid land research and management* 29(3), 360–374.

Kosmas C, Detsis V, Karamesouti M, Kounalaki K, Vassiliou P, Salvati L. (2015). Exploring Long-Term Impact of Grazing Management on Land Degradation in the Socio-Ecological System of Asteroussia Mountains, Greece. *Land*, 4(3):541–559.

Kosmas, C., N. Danalatos, L. H. Cammeraat, M. Chabart, J. Diamantopoulos, R. Farand, L. Gutiérrez, A. Jacob, H. Marques, J. Martínez-Fernández, A. Mizara, N. Moustakas, J. M. Nicolau, C. Oliveros, G. Pinna, R. Puddu, J. Puigdefábregas, M. Roxo, A. Simao, G. Stamou, N. Tomasi, D. Usai, and A. Vacca (1997). The effect of land use on runoff and soil erosion rates under Mediterranean conditions. *Catena* 29: 45–59.

Kosmas, C.; Kirkby, M.; Geeson, N. Manual on: Key Indicators of Desertification and Mapping Environmentally Sensitive Areas to Desertification; EUR 18882; European Commission-Energy, Environment and Sustainable Development: Brussels, Belgium, 1999; p. 87.

Marques, M. J., R. Bienes, L. Jiménez, and R. Pérez-Rodríguez (2007). Effect of vegetal cover on runoff and soil erosion under light intensity events. Rainfall simulation over USLE plots. *Science of the Total Environment* 378: 161–165.

Papanastasis, V.P. Livestock grazing in Mediterranean ecosystems: An historical and policy perspective. In *Ecological Basis of Livestock Grazing in Mediterranean Ecosystems*, Proceedings of the EU International Workshop, Thessaloniki, Greece, 23–25 October 1997; Papanastasis, V.P., Peter, D., Eds.; European Commission Science, Research and Development: Bruxelles, Belgium, 1998; pp. 5–9.

Papanastasis, V. P., Bautista, S., Chouvardas, D., Mantzanas, K., Papadimitriou, M., Mayor, A. G., ... & Vallejo, R. V. (2017). Comparative assessment of goods and services provided by grazing regulation and reforestation in degraded Mediterranean rangelands. *Land Degradation & Development* 28(4), 1178–1187.

Peco, B., A. M. Sánchez, and F. M. Azcárate (2006). Abandonment in grazing systems: Consequences for vegetation and soil. *Agriculture, Ecosystems & Environment* 113: 284–294.

Rubio, J.L.; Bochet, E. (1998). Desertification indicators as diagnosis criteria for desertification risk assessment in Europe. *J. Arid Environ.* 39, 113–120.

Salvati, L.; Bajocco, S. (2011). Land sensitivity to desertification across Italy: Past, present, and future. *Appl. Geogr.* 31, 223–231.

Sharma, K. D., D. E. Walling, and J. L. Probst. (1997). Assessing the impact of overgrazing on soil erosion in arid regions at a range of spatial scales. Human impact on erosion and sedimentation, pp. 119–123. Proceedings of an International Symposium of the Fifth Scientific Assembly of the International Association of Hydrological Sci. (IAHS), Rabat, Morocco.

Simeonakis, A.; Calvo-Cases, E.; Arnau-Rosalen, A. (2007). Land use change and land degradation in southeastern Mediterranean Spain. *Environ. Manag.* 40, 80–94.

Stefanakis, M., P. Volanis, I. Zoiopoulos, and K. Hadjigeorgiou. (2007). Assessing the potential benefits of technical intervention in evolving the semi-intensive dairy-sheep farms in Crete. *Small Ruminant Research* 72: 66–72.

Thornes, J.B. Stability, and instability in the management of Mediterranean desertification. In *Environmental Modelling: Finding Simplicity in Complexity*; Wainwright, J., Mulligan, M., Eds.; John Wiley & Sons: Chichester, UK, 2004; pp. 303–315.

Tsiourlis, G.M.; Kasapidis, P.; Parmakelis, A.; Dretakis, M. Effects of grazing on the structure of phryganic ecosystems in the Asterousia mountain of Crete, Greece. In *Ecological Basis of Livestock Grazing in Mediterranean Ecosystems, Proceedings of the International Workshop, Thessaloniki, Greece, 23–25 October 1997*; Papanastasis, V.P., Peter, D., Eds.; European Commission Science, Research and Development: Bruxelles, Belgium, 1998; pp. 94–97.

Zervas, G. (1998). Quantifying and optimizing grazing regimes in Greek mountain systems. *J. Appl. Ecol.* 35, 983–986

The Social Dimension of Nature-Based Solutions (NbSs)

Premise

There has been extensive debate surrounding natural-based solutions (NbSs) in recent years (European Commission, 2015). These solutions are defined as comprehensive strategies that address climate change, biodiversity conservation, and ecosystem service support through natural processes that are inherent in the water cycle, such as lamination, infiltration, and retention (Babí Almenar et al., 2021), and the carbon cycle. NbSs are designed to set up connections between ecological and economic benefits by incorporating multiple considerations that are of interest to various stakeholders. Unfortunately, policy documents and guidelines often overlook the social aspects of NbSs, including the changing costs and benefits that arise from their implementation. Although a few reports have addressed this issue, such as the Impact Evaluation of NbS by the EC, which examined societal challenges, particularly in the domain of "social justice and social cohesion," economic and environmental assessments that disregard social effects are considered ineffective. However, the effects of NbSs on social and environmental matters have not been adequately deliberated from a social-environmental perspective (Berbes-Blazquez et al., 2019; Dushkova et al., 2021; Kabisch et al., 2016). If NbSs are not socially and environmentally just, they may not distribute benefits and result in severe conflicts (Giordano et al., 2020; Guerrin et al., 2015; Kotsila et al., 2021).

NbS is an umbrella term for other concepts, such as green infrastructure (GI) and blue-green infrastructure (BGI). However, NbS emphasizes the value of nature in addressing societal challenges more than the other concepts do. Although NbS may align biodiversity features with sustainable livelihoods and flood management, it has not been adequately reviewed from social justice perspective (Dushkova et al., 2021). Reports by the European Commission and the International Union for Conservation of Nature (IUCN) have not addressed the fact that NbSs are implemented in areas with ongoing socio-economic and socio-spatial disparities. Instead, they have been politicized in a vague and uncontextualized manner, overlooking socio-environmental justice trade-offs (Haase, 2017). This is a significant issue that also occurs in broader climate action strategies where justice-related issues are not mainstreamed.

In this context, Hughes and Hoffmann (2020) introduced the idea of Just Urban Transitions as an agenda that strives to reconfigure power, and political barriers, and empower new actors in sustainable transitions. Similarly, Guerrin et al. (2015) argue that natural resources are deeply political, implying that different actors defend their interests and positions of power in transitions that involve the reconfiguration of socio-natural assets.

It is misleading to assume that NbSs can balance the triple challenge of economic, environmental, and social sustainability (Turkelboom et al., 2017). Although NbSs produce positive synergies, they create unequal outcomes among different population groups. NbSs are not inherently socially just and inclusive and may result in problematic social and environmental trade-offs (Dushkova et al., 2021; Haase, 2017). These trade-offs occur when the provision of ecosystem services (ES) is conditioned by other ES or when some stakeholders appropriate specific ES at the expense of others (Rodríguez et al., 2006). ES is defined as the benefits of nature for people in social, economic, and environmental terms (Diaz et al., 2015; Turner et al., 2016). The analysis of trade-offs is critical as the planning and implementation of i.e. certain types of flood management strategies come at the expense of others, creating winners and losers (Turner et al., 2016). The win-win discourse that greening projects seem to inspire at first glance has been thoroughly contested by critical environmental studies, geography, and political ecology, among others (Howe et al., 2014; Sekulova et al., 2021). Although political and social interests are present in most cases where NbSs are implemented, economic pressures on land uses, resulting in critical barriers to developing NbSs, are significant aspects of development (Li et al., 2019). Neglecting the unequal consequences of trade-offs among stakeholders, considering that some of them may be underrepresented in the implementation process, may lead to conflict and opposition to NbSs (Sowińska-Świerkosza & Michalik-Śnieżek, 2020).

In projects that involve NbSs, social acceptance is crucial, as seen in the energy transitions field. Social acceptance is defined as the combination of three dimensions: socio-political, market, and community. Socio-political acceptance refers to the acceptance among different stakeholders from the public to policymakers. Market acceptance refers to the relationships between investors and consumers. Lastly, community acceptance refers to how the local stakeholders engage in accepting NbS technologies and projects, linked to procedural justice,

distributional justice, and trust and recognition justice (Sari et al., 2018). These three categorizations of justice are articulated as drivers that show how "just" NbS can be, leading to acceptance among communities (Toxopeus et al., 2020). Procedural justice refers to levels and forms of participatory processes in decision-making. The successful implementation of Nature-based Solutions (NbSs) requires careful consideration of several factors. These include governance-related factors, such as institutional ability, political commitment, legal frameworks, mechanisms of feedback, access to financing, positive public image, and product costs (Anguelovski et al., 2018; Kanogu & Soytaş, 2018; Sovacool & Ratan, 2012). Additionally, the distribution of costs and benefits associated with NbSs must be equitable to ensure distributional justice (Cole et al., 2017). Community acceptance of NbSs depends on the benefits they generate at the local level, as perceived by local stakeholders. It is worth noting that the perceived benefits may differ, and there may be divergence in co-benefits and unequal trade-offs (Anderson & Renaud, 2021). As such, scrutinizing the distribution of costs and the effectiveness of NbSs in reducing risks is necessary for ensuring outcome efficacy. Moreover, recognizing diverse needs and values is crucial to ensure that NbSs are implemented in a just and equitable manner. This involves identifying the different dimensions of a community, such as race, gender, age, and ethnicity (Kabisch et al., 2014). Problem diagnosis and perception, as well as place attachment, are the first elements that compromise NbSs, as they imply different ways of valuing and relating to nature (Byrne, 2012). However, these challenges can be addressed through trust among stakeholders and non-hidden agendas.

To conclude, the concept of Nature-based Solutions (NbS) is built upon the principles of diversity, inclusion, and symbiosis. It emphasizes the importance of collective social learning and a blend of diverse knowledge to create effective and sustainable solutions. Take for instance, designing a drainage system that imitates the water-absorbing and filtration capabilities of wetlands to prevent urban flooding and restore vegetation on degraded hill slopes. This requires a combination of ecological and engineering knowledge, as well as traditional ecological knowledge from local communities. For NbS to be successful, it must have the support and commitment of both state and non-state actors, with a focus on gender equality and social inclusion. This is essential to address the needs, preferences, and vulnerabilities of diverse stakeholders, especially women, youth, differently abled individuals

and marginalized communities. Studies show that women are at a higher risk during natural disasters, particularly when poverty and discrimination intersect. Collaborative governance can promote wider social learning, awareness, and ownership, which are vital in the successful implementation of NbS.

Essential bibliography

Anderson, C.C.; Renaud, F.G. (2021). A Review of Public Acceptance of Nature-Based Solutions: The ‘why’, ‘When’, and ‘how’ of success for Disaster Risk Reduction Measures. *Ambio*, 50, 1552–1573.

Anguelovski, I.; Connolly, J.J.T.; Masip, L.; Pearsall, H. (2018). Assessing green gentrification in historically disenfranchised neighborhoods: A longitudinal and spatial analysis of Barcelona. *Urban Geogr.*, 39, 458–491.

Babí Almenar, J.; Elliot, T.; Rugani, B.; Philippe, B.; Navarrete Gutierrez, T.; Sonnemann, G.; Geneletti, D. (2021). Nexus between nature-based solutions, ecosystem services and urban challenges. *Land Use Policy*, 100, 104898.

Berbes-Blazquez, M.; Gonzales, J.A.; Pasqual, U. (2016). Towards an ecosystem services approach that addresses social power relations. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.*, 19, 134–143.

Byrne, J. (2012). When green is White: The cultural politics of race, nature, and social exclusion in a Los Angeles urban national park. *Geoforum*, 43, 595–611.

Cole, H.V.S.; Lamarca, M.G.; Connolly, J.J.T.; Anguelovski, I. (2017). Are green cities healthy and equitable? Unpacking the relationship between health, green space, and gentrification. *J. Epidemiol. Community Health*, 71, 1118–1121.

Díaz, S.; Demissew, S.; Carabias, J.; Joly, C.; Lonsdale, M.; Ash, N.; Larigauderie, A.; Adhikari, J.R.; Arico, S.; Báldi, A.; et al. (2015). The IPBES Conceptual Framework—Connecting nature and people. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.*, 14, 1–16.

Dushkova, D.; Haase, A.; Wolff, M.; Haase, D. (2021). Editorial for Special Issue “Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) in Cities and Their Interactions with Urban Land, Ecosystems, Built Environments and People: Debating Societal Implications”. *Land*, 10, 937.

European Commission (EC). *Towards an EC Research and Innovation Policy Agenda of Nature-Based Solutions and Re-Naturing Cities*; European Commission (EC): Brussels, Belgium, 2015.

Giordano, R.; Pluchinotta, I.; Pagano, A.; Scricciu, A. (2020). Enhancing nature-based solutions acceptance through stakeholders’ engagement in co-benefits identification and trade-offs analysis. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 713, 136552.

Guerrin, J. (2015). A floodplain restoration project on the river Rhône (France): Analyzing challenges to its implementation. *Reg. Environ. Chang.*, 15, 559–568.

Haase, A. The Contribution of Nature-Based Solutions to Socially Inclusive Urban Development—Some Reflections from a Social-environmental Perspective. In *Nature-Based Solutions to Climate Change Adaptation in Urban Areas*; Nadja Kabisch, N., Korn, H., Stadler, J., Bonn, A., Eds.; Springer International Publishing: Cham, Switzerland, 2017; pp. 221–236.

Howe, C.; Suich, H.; Vira, B.; Mace, G.M. (2014). Creating win-win from trade-offs? Ecosystem services for human well-being: A meta-analysis of ecosystem service trade-offs and synergies in the real world. *Glob. Environ. Chang.*, 28, 263–275.

Hughes, S.; Hoffmann, M. (2020). Just urban transitions: Toward a research agenda. *WIREs Clim. Chang.*, 11, e640.

Kabisch, N.; Frantzeskaki, N.; Pauleit, S.; Naumann, S.; Davis, M.; Artmann, M.; Haase, D.; Knapp, S.; Korn, H.; Stadler, J.; et al. (2016). Nature-based solutions to climate change mitigation and adaptation in urban areas: Perspectives on indicators, knowledge gaps, barriers, and opportunities for action. *Ecol. Soc.*, 21, 39

Kabisch, N.; Haase, D. (2014). Green justice or just green? Provision of urban green spaces in Berlin, Germany. *Landsc. Urban Plan.*, 122, 129–139.

Kanogu, D.G.; Soytaş, U. (2018). The Impact of Information Provision on the Social Acceptance of Shale Gas Development: A Review-Based Inclusive Model. *Front. Energy Res.*, 6, 1–13.

Kotsila, P.; Anguelovski, I.; Baró, F.; Langemeyer, J.; Sekulova, F.; Connolly, J. (2021). Nature-based solutions as discursive tools and contested practices in urban nature's neoliberalisation processes. *Environ. Plan. E Nat. Space*, 4, 252–274.

Li, C.; Gao, X.; He, B.-J.; Wu, J.; Wu, K. (2019). Coupling Coordination Relationships between Urban-industrial Land Use Efficiency and Accessibility of Highway Networks: Evidence from Beijing-Tianjin-Hebei Urban Agglomeration, China. *Sustainability*, 11, 1446.

Rodríguez, J.P.; Beard, T.D., Jr.; Bennett, E.M.; Cumming, G.S.; Cork, S.J.; Agard, J.; Dobson, A.P.; Peterson, G.D. (2006). Trade-offs across space, time, and ecosystem services. *Ecol. Soc.*, 11, 28

Sari, R.; Soytaş, U.; Kanoglu, D.; Ates, A.M.; Islambay, D.; Kilic, C.; Breuker, S. D5.3—Values of Societal Acceptance. Report for Project Nature4cities: Nature Based Solutions for Re-Naturing Cities: Knowledge Diffusion and Decision Support Platform through New Collaborative Models. 2018.

Sekulova, F.; Anguelovski, I.; Kiss, B.; Kotsila, P.; Baró, F.; Voytenko Palgan, Y.; Connolly, J. (2021). The governance of nature-based solutions in the city at the intersection of justice and equity. *Cities*, 112, 103136.

Sovacool, B.K.; Ratan, P.L. (2012). Conceptualizing the acceptance of wind and solar electricity. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, 16, 5268–5279.

Sowińska-Świerkosza, B.; Michalik-Śnieżek, M. (2020). The methodology of Landscape Quality (LQ) indicators analysis based on remote sensing data: Polish National Parks Case Study. *Sustainability*, 12, 2810

Toxopeus, H.; Kotsila, P.; Conde, M.; Katona, A.; van der Jagt, A.P.N.; Polzin, F. (2020). How 'just' is hybrid governance of urban nature-based solutions? *Cities*, 105, 102839.

Turkelboom, F.; Leone, M.; Jacobs, S.; Kelemen, E.; García-Llorente, M.; Baró, F.; Termansen, M.; Barton, D.N.; Berry, P.; Stange, E.; et al. (2018). When we cannot have it all: Ecosystem services tradeoffs in the context of spatial planning. *Ecosyst. Serv.*, 29, 566–578.

Turner, K.G.; Anderson, S.; Gonzales-Chang, M.; Costanza, R.; Courville, S.; Dalgaard, T.; Dominati, E.; Kubiszewski, I.; Ogilvy, S.; Porfirio, L.; et al. (2016). A review of methods, data, and models to assess changes in the value of ecosystem services from land degradation and restoration. *Ecol. Model.*, 319, 190–207.